

MULTIPLE ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON THE CREEP BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The strength and stiffness properties of carbonfiber-reinforced resins are time-, temperature- and moisture-dependent especially in the case of matrix-controlled laminates. The degradation of the elastic and thermal properties can be assessed by lamination theory stipulating linear viscoelastic behaviour and material laws depending on strain history.

The experimental part of related research effort involved the testing of $[\pm 45^{\circ}_3]_s$ laminates made from 914C/T300 material. Before and after thermal cycling, which induced matrix cracking, dry and moisturized specimens were loaded to 30 % of their ultimate tensile strengths and were subjected to elevated temperatures and relative humidities corresponding to the storage conditions for 200 hours. The creep modulus of elasticity showed a significant dependence on temperature, moisture and matrix crack density.

The analytical part of the study was performed by Dornier-System using the ADVLAM computer program, which offers the possibility of linear viscoelastic calculations. Only the Young's modulus E_{22} and the shear modulus G_{12} are time dependent; E_{22} is derived from the rule of mixture. Horizontal temperature - moisture shift factors permitted strain and stress calculations for the tested laminates. A vertical time shift factor accounted for the effect of matrix cracking.

Good correlations with the experimental data were obtained. The analysis results of laminates presented found an application on a sandwich structure.

SCOPE OF TEST PROGRAM

For the investigation of the material response under multiple environmental conditions, e.g. time, temperature and moisture, before and after thermal cycling between 100 °C and -160 °C in vacuum, which induced matrix cracking, a $[\pm 45^{\circ}_3]_s$ -laminate configuration made from 914C/T300 material was tested. Each of the test specimens consisted of 12 plies of 0.125 mm thickness. The test specimens were 100 mm long and 15 mm wide without end reinforcement. In correlation with a previous research program [1] on neat resin BSL 914 the test conditions chosen for the measurement of creep deformations up to 200 hours chosen were $T = 20, 60, 80$ °C and ~ 10 and ~ 50 % R. H. for all three temperatures. The selected load level was 30 % of the ultimate tensile strength of such laminate type at 80 °C/ 50 % R.H. according to the test results in [2]. The specimens were stored before testing at the same relative humidity until the weight of the specimens stabilized at the saturation moisture content. In addition, it should be mentioned that the required moisture content of those specimens, cycled in a dry state, was introduced after cycling.

CREEPING TESTS

1. TEST PROCEDURE

A climate chamber was used in which the specimens were loaded by a balance system which enables a load magnification of 1:10. The chamber is fitted with steel girders which act as both fastening points for the clamps and as fulcrum for the balance system. The chamber is insulated with stonewool and/or polystyrol and aluminum foil. The temperature can be adjusted by a thyristor control device to within a range of ± 0.5 K. The temperature is monitored by three thermoclements. The moisture is controlled by a specific measuring device for the relative humidity. Deformation was measured inductively by specially developed gages which provide direct impulses for a plotter. The monitoring frequency was 10 measurements per decade. Five tests were done for each parameter combination to get an average value.

2. RESULTS

After measuring the creep as function of time, temperature, moisture content and crack density, the creep modulus was evaluated as function of time, which is defined within the linear area as:

$$E_C = \frac{\sigma_c}{\epsilon(t)} \quad (1)$$

More detailed information about this evaluation procedure can be found in [1].

All curves were shifted to the shortest test period of $\log t = -2$, which means 10^{-2} hours ($= 36$ s). Master curves were drawn by shifting the temperature curves themselves and changing the definition of the time axis.

The summary of the final experimental results can be depicted from Figure 1, which show the creep moduli in dependence of relative humidities and damage states. Up to $t = 100$ h or $\log t = 2$ a more or less linear viscoelastic response of the test material can be derived for the uncycled and cycled, wet and dry test specimens, respectively. From thereon a more nonlinear viscoelastic response is observed. An uncommon behavior is that the cracked test pieces have a higher creep modulus than the non-cracked ones.

Fig. 1 Summary of experimentally derived Master curve of time-dependent creep moduli E_C .

ANALYTICAL CORRELATIONS

1. LINEAR VISCOELASTIC ANALYSIS

The calculations are based on the ADVLAM code [3] in which linear viscoelastic analysis is implemented and which therefore allows to predict time dependent material behavior. The constitutive law equation

$$\sigma_i = Q_{ij} (\epsilon_j - \alpha_j \Delta T - \beta_j \Delta M - \epsilon_j^*) \quad (2)$$

is based upon the integral formulation of the form

$$\sigma_i(T, M, t) = \int_{0^+}^t Q_{ij}(T, M, t - \tau) \frac{d\bar{\epsilon}_j(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

with

$$\bar{\epsilon}_j(\tau) = \epsilon_j(\tau) - \alpha_j \Delta T(\tau) - \beta_j \Delta M(\tau) \quad (4)$$

where the Q_{ij} are defined as relaxation moduli.

Introducing the concept of time-temperature-moisture superposition permits the use of a master relaxation modulus curve representation of the experimental data given by

$$Q_{ij}(T, M, t) = a_v(T, M) \cdot Q_{ij}(T_0, M_0, \xi) \quad (5)$$

where T_0 and M_0 are the reference temperature and moisture conditions for the master curve, a_v is the vertical shift factor, and ξ is the reduced time defined as

$$\xi = \int_{0^+}^t \frac{d\xi}{a_{TM}(T, M)} \quad (6)$$

with a_{TM} being the horizontal temperature-moisture shift factor. Substituting (5) into (3) and integrating by parts yields

$$\sigma_i(T, M, t) = Q_{ij}(T, M, 0) \bar{\epsilon}_j(t) - \int_{0^+}^t \frac{d[a_v(T, M) \cdot Q_{ij}(T_0, M_0, \xi - \xi')]}{d\tau} \bar{\epsilon}_j(\tau) d\tau \quad (7)$$

which is the form of the equation used in the ADVLAM code. The integral term of (7) can be identified as the $Q_{ij} \epsilon_j'$ term in (2). In order to use (7) in a numerical scheme, it is necessary to simplify the integral and, at the same time, express the relaxation moduli, Q_{ij} , in some functional form so that the necessary time derivative may be taken. Thus, the relaxation moduli are expanded in a finite exponential series of the form

$$Q_{ij}(T_0, M_0, \xi) = Q_{ij}(T_0, M_0, 0) - \sum_{k=1}^n F_{ij}^k(T_0, M_0) \cdot [1 - e^{-\lambda_{ij}^k \xi}] \quad (8)$$

The shift factor a_{TM} as a function of temperature and moisture permits calculating new creep moduli according to different environmental conditions. The shift factor a_v as a function of time and temperature describes various creep moduli for the same time. Microcrack behavior of the material, caused by temperature cycling effects [4], is taken into account by the shift factor a_v . Both factors (horizontal and vertical) are used to translate the material behavior from short time tests at high temperatures to low temperatures, long times and moderate loading. So, these short time tests are less expensive and less time consuming. The assumption for the application of this procedure is linear material behavior. Further on there are no changes in chemical structure as well as shrinkage from moisture desorption.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE MASTER CURVE

The data base of the viscoelastic calculations is the material 914C/T300. The engineering constants interpolated for three temperatures and a relative humidity of 13 % from [5] show that only the Young's modulus E_{22} and the shear modulus G_{12} are temperature dependent. The Young's modulus E_{11} is nearly constant and the Poisson's ratio ν_{12} is constant. Supposing the same time behavior for E_{22} and G_{12} only one parameter has to be tested and included in the ADVLAM code.

To describe the time behavior of the material, basically there are two possibilities

- the creep deformations of a UD - laminate under transverse tensile loading (test data) are employed
- the Young's modulus E_{22} of a UD - laminate is calculated by the creep behavior of the neat resin (E_m) and the Young's modulus of the fiber ($E_f = \text{const.}$) using the rule of mixture by the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{E_{22}} = \frac{\varphi_f}{E_f} + \frac{1 - \varphi_f}{E_m} \quad (9)$$

with φ_f as fiber content.

Basically the two different ways result in curves incompatible to each other. At a time of $\log t = -2$ the Young's moduli of the test results are about 9 % higher than the corresponding calculated values. The gradient of the test data is substantially smaller (linear domain) than for the calculated data. Obviously, a stiffening effect occurs under transverse tensile loading by interaction of fiber and matrix. This effect can not be observed for the time behavior of the neat resin.

The E_{22} behavior is therefore calculated with the creep deformation of the neat resin from [1].

With (9) and the Young's modulus E_{11} from [5] the time dependent material behavior of a UD - laminate is described. The master curve is determined at $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$. This curve already shows the degradation of E_{22c} (transverse creep modulus) over a period of about 100 h. Within this time the modulus of elasticity decreases from $E_{22} = 8\,300$ to $6\,980 \text{ N/mm}^2$ which means a reduction of about 16 %.

3. LAMINATE ANALYSIS BASED ON STRAIN-TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT PROPERTIES

The master curve displays the time dependent distribution of the creep modulus at $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$. However, the application of the horizontal temperature shift factor permits the prediction of creep moduli at other temperatures.

The shift factors are valid for linear material behavior. They are derived graphically from the creep moduli as a function of time and temperature and the employed horizontal factors were specified for a moisture content of about $M = 0\%$ as $a_{TM} = 2.14$ and 3.50 for $T = 60$ and 80°C , respectively.

The analyses are performed for a symmetric balanced $[\pm 45^\circ_3]_s$ laminate with a thickness of $t = 1\text{ mm}$. Two different load cases are introduced into the laminate by thermal loads due to cooling down from the curing temperature of $T = 175^\circ\text{C}$.

The mechanical loading is assumed to be $\sigma_x = 54\text{ N/mm}^2$ which is about 30% of ultimate tensile strength. The time of the loading was fixed to $t = 100\text{ h}$. The comparison of analytical and test results showed the same material characteristic but the time dependent creep moduli had a too high level (around 14%). Therefore the starting points of the curve distributions at $\log t = -2$ were constructed. This was accommodated by changing the engineering constants E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} to see the most sensitive controlling factor. It appeared that only the shear modulus G_{12} had great influence on the magnitude of the creep moduli. This investigation yields to a reduction of 15% for the shear modulus G_{12} which is shown in the following table together with all UD-values used for the calculation:

T	R. H.	E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{12}	ν_{12}
$^\circ\text{C}$	%	KN/mm ²			—
22	13	134.0	9.46	4.30	0.32
60	13	135.9	8.99	4.55	0.32
80	13	136.8	8.42	4.70	0.32

The effects of moisture on the time dependent response in composites were investigated for the same type of laminate. The saturation moisture content is about $M = 0.3\%$. The shift factor is defined by $a_{TM} = -0.1$, which means higher creep moduli. This material behavior under moisture content is also in accordance with the results of [5]. Calculating the time dependent coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) a thermal load case with a temperature difference of $\Delta T = 1\text{ K}$ is defined (unit load case). Then the resulting creep deformations (strains) represent simultaneously the time dependent CPE's and were calculated for $T = 20$, 60 and 80°C with a moisture content of $M = 0\%$.

4. LAMINATE ANALYSIS BASED ON MICROCRACK EXPANSION

The different stiffness values of E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} for the fiber and matrix of a layup lead to shear stresses at the fiber-matrix interface (tensile loadings). Resulting local peak loads are reduced by creep effects between fiber and matrix.

Microcracking under load is caused by temperature cycling effects including initial stress state by temperature and moisture content. This matrix behavior can be described by the linear viscoelastic theory. In this calculation microcrack effects are taken into account by the vertical shift factor a_v considering not only the temperature dependence of the material, but also the time dependence of cycling tests.

The temperature cycled specimens showed at $T = 60$ and 80°C a stiffness dissipation of the creep moduli whereas there was a stiffness increase at $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$ compared to the uncycled test. This unusual effect is valid for dry test specimens (Figure 2a) and is in contradiction to the wet specimens, where a stiffness increase was observed for all temperatures (see Figure 2b).

a Creep moduli (dry state) exp. and analytical

b Creep moduli (wet state) experimental

Fig. 2 Comparison of creep moduli of a $[\pm 45^\circ_3]_s$ - laminate, uncycled and cycled.

The following assumption is made for the material behavior in the dry state:

- The time-shift factor of cycled laminates is zero at the temperature $T = 40^\circ\text{C}$,
- the shift factor is negative at $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$, e. g. transformation to higher creep moduli,
- consequently the shift factors are positive above $T = 40^\circ\text{C}$.

Between the defined shift factors it is assumed to interpolate linearly. The time shift factors are derived empirically varying as long as the creep moduli correspond to the test results at the time of $\log t = -2$. Due to the master curve following shift factors are derived:

T	°C	20	40	60	80
a_v	-	- 0.843	0.000	0.960	0.970

The material law and the load cases for the analysis of the cycled specimens are identical with the uncycled ones.

COMPARISON OF ANALYTICAL AND TEST RESULTS

The calculations attempted by ADVLAM are realized up to the time $t = 100$ h of loading. From there on a nonlinear viscoelastic response of the test material is observed (see Figure 1).

The comparison of the analytical and test results led to the following:

- There is an excellent agreement for the uncycled specimens at $T = 20, 60$ and 80°C . Beyond $t = 10$ h the nonlinear material behavior of the test specimens already appears.
- There is a good agreement for the cycled specimens microcrack behavior, especially at $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$. The calculated data for $T = 60^\circ\text{C}$ are somewhat below the test results. At $T = 80^\circ\text{C}$ the analytical results are higher than the test results. The difference is about 5%. The time dependent material behavior of a wet laminate shows differences between test and analytical results. This effect of moisture can be explained by different time behavior of E_{22} and G_{12} which has more influence on the viscoelastic material behavior. This significant increase in creep with humidity was also observed by K.G. Kibler [6] and can be described with a second master curve valid for the time dependence of G_{12} .
- Separate input for time dependent material behavior of E_{22} and G_{12} is realized in the program, so it is possible to analyze laminates also for wet environmental conditions, e. g. the results in Figure 2b.

ANALYSIS OF A SANDWICH STRUCTURE

An application of the analysis results is demonstrated with a sandwich structure which reflects the time dependent material behavior under a defined load case by analyzing the time dependent deflections.

The sandwich panel is given by:

	Face sheets	Core
Material	914C/T300	Honeycomb
laminate	[+ 45° / - 45°]	-
thickness	[0.5 mm / 0.5 mm]	20 mm
width	1 mm	1 mm
length	1000 mm	1000 mm

The unidirectional material data base of the face sheets is mentioned previously.

- Boundary conditions: The upper end of the sandwich is free, the lower one is fixed (cantilever beam)
- Load case: The bending moment at the upper end of the sandwich $M = 100 \text{ Nmm}$
- Deflections: The deflections w at $x = l$ are calculated by the analyzed middle surface curvatures κ_x and the equation

$$\kappa_x = - \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \quad (10)$$

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the deflections at the end of the panel. Within the time of $t = 100$ h the deflection increases from $w = 13.53$ up to 15.69 mm which means about 16 %.

Fig. 3 Specimen configuration, boundary conditions, load case and time dependent deflection of the sandwich panel $[\pm 45^\circ/3/16 - 5052 - .001/\pm 45^\circ]$.

CONCLUSIONS

The master curve of the material 914C/T300 valid for dry test specimens, uncycled and cycled is derived. Wet specimens have a different material behavior as the corresponding dry ones. The greater influence of the shear modulus G_{12} and the smaller for the transverse modulus E_{22} of a $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ -laminates requires two master curves (E_{22}, G_{12}), which can be implemented in the ADVLAM code separately.

The time dependent material behaviour of a $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ angle-ply laminate is calculated by using time-temperature-moisture shift factors at $T = 60$ and 80°C . Comparing analyses and test results very good agreement can be found. Microcrack behavior, realized by temperature cycling effects, can be verified for this laminate as well. However, it was only possible to compare test and analytical data up to the time $t = 100$ h (linear domain).

For that the assumption contains a safe data base prescribing an exact material behavior and choosing small interpolation steps.

REFERENCES

1. Niederstadt G and Klinger G, Simulation of Longtime Loading Tests on Polymers by using a Time-Temperature Shift Method acc. to Williams, Landel, Ferry. DFVLR IB 131-86/27 Braunschweig (1986).
2. Gädke M, Response of Laminates Under Static Compression Loading, in: Development of Fracture Mechanics Maps for Composite Materials - Compression Loading, Final Report, ESA-ESTEC Contract No. 6400/85/NL/PB(SC) (1988), pp. 61 - 132.
3. Flagg D L, ADVLAM, An Advanced Composite Laminate Analysis Code, Lockheed Palo Alto Research Laboratory (1986).
4. Hartung W, Influence of Thermal Cycling on Material Properties, in: Development of Fracture Mechanics Maps for Composite Materials - Compression Loading, Final Report, ESA-ESTEC Contract No. 6400/85/NL/PB(SC) (1988), pp. 262 -293.
5. Gädke M, Hygrothermomechanisches Verhalten kohlenstoffaserverstärkter Epoxidharze, Hygrothermomechanical Behaviour of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxies, VDI-Fortschritt-Bericht R 5/136 (1988).
6. Kibler K G, Time Dependent Environment Behaviour of Epoxy Matrix Composites, Material Research Laboratory, General Dynamics, Ft. Worth (1979).